

The use of Social Return on Investment approaches to evaluate Integrated Long-term Care solutions: A Scoping Review

As older adults have more complex needs, health and social care services need to work better together. This scoping review aims to identify and analyse SROI approaches within LTC.

OBJECTIVES OF THE SCOPING REVIEW

- Identify and analyse in how far SROI is used within LTC.
- Summarise what outcomes were measured, how they were monetised, and what the reported SROI were.
- Identify gaps, limits, and next steps for better evidence.

How we did it (Method)

Search & screening

- **Timeframe:** 2012–2024.
- **Sources:** medical/social care databases plus grey literature and citation chasing.
- **Three reviewers** screened records and extracted data using a structured approach.

What was included?

- English-language **SROI** studies in **high-income countries**.
- Focus on **integrated LTC** (health and social care working together), mainly for older adults.

What we looked at (Scope)

- Interventions mainly delivered in the community and at home, with some links to primary care and residential settings.
- Most studies described coordination approaches (a mid-level form of integration involving structured collaboration across health and social care); a few linkage approaches (the first, lower level of integration, based mainly on referral and communication).

What we found (Results)

The evidence base

- 556 records screened → 11 studies included.
- Predominantly United Kingdom (UK)-based (one study from Singapore).
- Mix of academic papers.

Outcomes that were measured

- **For people:** physical and mental health, independence, skills (personal resources).
- **For communities:** social connections, participation (community resources).
- **For public services:** knock-on effects like fewer General Practitioner (GP) visits or less pressure on hospitals (public resources).
- **Negative outcomes:** increased investment needs, adverse job satisfaction (rarely reported).

How changes were turned into money

- Primarily based on established UK proxy databases (e.g. HACT Social Value Bank) and real-world prices (e.g. GP appointments, care-home places).
- UK-centric sources can make it harder to transfer figures to other countries.

The SROI results (with caveats)

- Almost all studies reported positive returns: roughly **£0.58 to over £5** back for every £1 invested.
- Ratios are context-specific (measuring the value created relative to the investment) and **should not be compared across different activities**.
- Some studies did not test how sensitive their findings were to key assumptions.

WHAT THIS MEANS

STRENGTHS

- SROI captures outcomes that matter to many groups: people using services, families, staff, funders, and communities.
- An SROI approach encourages a whole-society view, not just costs to one service.

LIMITATIONS

- Small samples, data gaps, and differences in methods and price proxies limit comparisons.
- Some studies missed sensitivity testing.
- Evidence is strongly UK-centred, which reduces generalisability.

WHAT'S NEEDED NEXT

- More studies beyond the UK and beyond English-only sources.
- Clearer, more consistent methods and reporting.
- Locally relevant price proxies.
- Broader outcome coverage where appropriate, including societal and environmental effects.

